

Use of the Holistic Gamified Learning Framework in implementing gamification through Edmodo for St. Dominic College of Asia

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Abstract

This paper explores the implementation of Gamification through the Holistic Gamified Learning Framework and its possibilities and repercussions of using gamification both in traditional method and via online platform based on review of several literatures. To do this, the proponent compared three possible frameworks to find out what framework is more suitable to be used in an implementation of a gamification strategy. It was found out that through Edmodo as a platform for gamification awards, this Holistic Gamified Learning Framework would be better to implement to the school for specific cases that will empower the student within their classes regardless of their program. The researcher found out that there should be needs for the implementation for the earlier generation teacher where gamification would be better explained and taught to them. This study could potentially serve as a model for instructors who want to include gamification into their own courses. Other organizations and schools can adapt gamification as a process of teaching and motivating their students at the same time.

Keywords: *Gamification, Learning Management System (LMS), Holistic Gamified Learning Framework, Edmodo.*

Introduction

Currently, the most used practice in teaching is based on what we call “*didactic learning*” or the so-called traditional curriculum, with subjects usually taught in lectures, presentations, seminars, and practicing through case studies (Sabolic et al., 2015). The problem is that some students find standard lessons boring and useless, and while many teachers explore unique ways to encourage their students, many struggled to connect in a meaningful way (Caponetto et al., 2014). Pupils in lessons today are bored. Teachers are having trouble engaging them in the material of schooling, which results in a low degree of participation (Lajord, 2016). In gamification, there is increased interest as a unique practice in the field of training and education (Cruaud, 2018).

One of the proponent’s task is to gather data from the target institution to be able to derive the problem. The data would be gathered with consideration on the retention of students to their initially preferred program the information of the student data came from the current semester and some data from the previous academic year.

There are few research papers that looks into the effects of gamification implemented on established contexts (Kelle et al., 2013). The current landscape of learning, the use of educational games, and gamification strategies used in instructional delivery, have been receiving attention as a means of increasing the engagement of learners regardless of age group, ethnicity, and context backgrounds. Even though gamification is fully implemented in the business, marketing, corporate and wellness sectors, the applications of gamification in the academic sector is still considered as an emerging trend (Dicheva et al., 2015).

Gamification in an academic perspective was used as an approach in supporting teaching and learning where teaching was designed to be more motivational learning experience through methods using game design to psychologically engage human playfulness that was existent in most students (Codish & Ravid, 2015). Gamification uses game concepts or game elements and implements it to non-game contexts (Poole et al., 2014). It has been observed that gamification concepts are found to motivate or incentivize the students through the use of points.

The problems in the study are reflected in the following statements:

- The mission of the institution is not being accurately hit due to the rate of shifting and student enrollment data, which suggests that students are reacting instead of being proactive.
- Regarding to the result of the preliminary survey and the weight value of each question to engagement according to the study made by K12 Insight (2012), the result shows that there is a gap or lack in engagement and motivation of students towards learning.

Thus, the study aims to achieve the following objectives: Design and implement a gamification strategy using Edmodo to improve engagement levels of students towards developing better organizational learning; Identify engagement activities aimed towards improving organizational learning for the institution; Identify expected behaviors of students for each activity; Identify optimum levels of engagement of students towards programs; Design a gamification strategy for faculty members implement through Edmodo for delivering courses with a goal of enhancing engagement levels of students toward the class; Provide a plan in delivering a more engaging and motivating platform of delivery of education aiming to influence students to behave proactively to scenarios; Examine the role of a learning management system (LMS) in conjunction with classroom instruction from the perspectives of users; and Design Intrinsic and Extrinsic rewards for each gamification milestone.

To determine what framework is best suited in implementing the gamification strategy for this proposal, the proponent compared three possible frameworks to find out what framework is more suitable to be used in an implementation of a gamification strategy. The three frameworks assessed for utilization in the research were the following:

- The Holistic Gamified Learning Framework (Jones, 2014)
- The five step process gamifying concepts (Huang and Soman, 2013)
- Octalysis – the complete gamification framework (Chou, 2019)

The Holistic Gamified Learning Framework

One thing to take note of, is that the framework is not a linear framework, which allows the user to consider aspects of learning to create a comfortable and meaningful learning experience (Jones, 2014).

Figure 1 Holistic Gamified Learning Framework (Jones, 2014)

The holistic gamified learning framework comprises of the following steps:

- Identify Gamification scope whether micro or macro;
- Define learning objectives;
- Identify learners and learning factors;
- Assess learners’ motivation;
- Design a narrative for player types;
- Choose materials and tools;
- Apply game principles and elements; and
- Identify whether the implementation scope of a gamification strategy is either a macro or micro gamification design.

Methodology

The proponent employed descriptive images to present the result of data such as pie chart and bar chart for categorical data. Mean, median, and mode were used to describe and summarize the gathered data.

The following are to be considered if the implementation aims to create learning narrative for cohesion, or to gamify the environment or create gamified activities, and blend the created narratives to activities. First, it is more inclined to a macro implementation of a gamification design while on the other hand, a gamification of the syllabus, the gradebook, assignments, and activities are part of a micro gamification design (Jones, 2014). The next step is to define learning goals and objectives to understand what to gamify. It should be identified what should be achieved and what optimal behavior such as passing assignments on time is targeted, completing work on time or even earlier and develop literacy and engage the students more (Jones, 2014).

The third step in the holistic gamification framework is identifying learners and what factors affect their learning (Jones, 2014). These factors can be captured through a survey which can gather data about the student's motivation for attending classes or the perspective of the learner towards the course relevance to their goals, the schedule is accepted by the learner and do open communication exist in the course? These factors are considered when doing the identification of the target learners (Jones, 2014).

Next is by assessing the learner's intrinsic motivation such as understanding who are your learners, do you understand what are their goals, habits, and identify what are the factors the gamification strategy will affect may it be initial, formative or summative such as what behavior to change, or does gamifying learning environment affect directly the rubric, grade and their portfolio (Jones, 2014). Having identified the factors that will be affected in the implementation of the gamification strategy, we are now able to design a narrative for our learner types to get the desired behavior of the learners, and we can assign the Bartle's test to determine what type of learner they would be and what concepts the narrative would address (Jones, 2014).

The next phase leads up to what materials and tools will be considered in implementing this gamification approach, if tracking of student's progress be approached through badges, points and leaderboards or if elements of gamification be created (Jones, 2014). Considering these factors leads us to our last step in the holistic gamification framework, which is the application of such principles and elements to achieve desirable responses from learners to influence behavior and promote repeated expected behavior from learners (Jones, 2014).

Analyzing the three frameworks presented, the proponent decided that the Holistic Gamified Learning Framework (HGL Framework) is the best fitted in the implementation of the proposed gamification strategy in the institution. Aside from the factors that the framework is nonlinear and simple to implement, the proponent considered also the definitions of the steps that is stated in the framework specially the step in which the identifying learning objectives, which is defined that in the framework it is perceived as the performance of the student in submitting classwork on time and the behavior of students in participating to activities. To ensure that a gamification strategy is one of the possible solutions, this factor is greatly considered, hence, the decision about the chosen gamification framework.

Results and Discussion

The following presents the results that are in percentage form to shorten the data.

Table 1 Summary of responses on the Holistic Gamified Learning Framework

Responses	1 (SD)	2 (D)	3 (N)	4 (A)	5 (SA)
The teachers talk about interesting subject/s in my classes.	3.0	3.9	23.5	36.5	33.1
My homework and other assignments are interesting to me.	3.4	5.6	32.6	33.8	24.5
My teachers spend enough time with me to help me do well.	3.3	7.0	31.2	33.7	24.8
I look forward to seeing what we will do in class each day.	3.3	6.4	27.8	35.4	27.0
The activities we do in class are fun and exciting.	3.8	5.8	29.0	35.3	26.1
My classes are teaching me skills that I need to be successful in life outside of school.	3.1	4.6	25.0	36.1	31.2
I participate in class discussions and other activities.	2.2	5.0	24.7	38.4	29.7
I feel that the activities we do in class help me to learn.	2.8	3.5	24.2	37.5	31.9
I feel that I have learned enough to prepare me for a career after graduation.	3.5	6.1	26.9	34.9	28.6
I am confident of the skills I have obtained during classes.	3.2	5.4	27.0	37.6	26.9

Note. SD – Strongly disagree; D – Disagree; N – Neutral; A – Agree; SA – Strongly agree

Based on the above table, most of the respondents agree that the teachers talk about interesting subjects in their classes (36.5%). Majority of the participants agree that their homework and other assignments are interesting to them (33.8%), while they agree that their teachers spend enough time with them to help them do well (33.7%). Most of the respondents agree that they look forward to seeing what they will do in class each day (35.4%), whereas they agree that their activities they do in class are fun and exciting (35.3%). It is also revealed that most participants agree that their classes were teaching them skills to be successful in life outside of school (36.1%) and that they participate in class discussions and other activities (38.4%). Students agree that the activities that they do in class help them to learn (37.5%), that they have learned enough to prepare them for a career after graduation (34.9%), and that they are confident of the skills that they have obtained during classes (37.6%). Majority of the respondents This shows that majority of the respondents “agree” in all of the statements given on the table.

The proponent of this research believes that this proposal would be useful for some specific situations. At St. Dominic College of Asia, gamification as a process of teaching or a technique in further reinforcing the organizational learning in has been slowly being accepted. Through Edmodo as a platform for gamification awards, this would be better to implement to the school for specific cases that will empower the student within their classes regardless of their program. The result of the research is similar to the results of other researches with similar implementations of gamification to learning (Aynsley et al., 2018 as cited in Hamari et al., 2016; Nadolny & Halabi, 2016; McDaniel and Fanfarelli, 2016).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Based on the surveys that the proponent conducted, the researcher is positive with the findings and the possibilities for additional research into the possibilities for using gamification in the education sector and across various courses to encourage students to use the tools and methodology offered to them during the courses. Adding a holistic gamification learning framework to the tools of Edmodo used within any course has proven to have significant effect on the amount of use by students. Gamification has a huge impact on not only engagement, involvement, and motivation, but also on the level of enjoyment students had in class, and their confidence on the knowledge they have gained have improved as well. Gamification has a huge amount of potential, as seen by the rich tradition on it, including the psychology behind it. It is increasingly being used by businesses and charity groups, including schools, to inspire employees, students, and customers (Burke, 2012).

Since this is the first implementation of the gamification framework to Edmodo in St. Dominic College of Asia, the future researchers can include in their plans the implementation of policy plans in which will ensure the use or increase usage of the used gamification framework.

It is also recommended that new ways of applying gamification to learning contexts be discovered and shared, including but not limited to extrinsic rewards such as achievements and badges that are more meaningful to students, as this is critical for increasing the use of this emerging technology in education. While the concept of gamification appears straightforward, the research shows that effectively gamifying learning is not.

For future researches, further improvement and development on how gamification can be implemented for other areas, and improving the methods used in this research should be considered. The researcher found out that there should be needs for the implementation for the earlier generation teacher where gamification would be better explained and taught to them. This study could potentially serve as a model for instructors who want to include gamification into their own courses. Other organizations and schools can adapt gamification as a process of teaching and motivating their students at the same time.

Another future step for this research is that other researchers may use other models to implement gamification. Other models could show that gamification has less benefits, or possibly that it has more. The suggestion of a new method of gamification is interesting, but it has yet to be tested. The researcher believes that gamification has so much potential, and influence regarding the norms of how we operate organizational learning. It may not be the form we see it now, but it may be in another extended form. It is very interesting for a researcher and hope to be able to contribute towards the evolution of implementing gamification across multiple disciplines.

References

- Aynsley, S. A., Nathawat, K., & Crawford, R. M. (2018). Evaluating student perceptions of using a game-based approach to aid learning: Braincept. *Higher Education Pedagogies*, 3(1), 478-489. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23752696.2018.1435296>

- Burke, B. (2012). *Gamification: Engagement strategies for business and IT*. Gartner. <https://www.gartner.com/en/documents/2246217/gamification-engagement-strategies-for-business-and-it>
- Caponetto, I., Earp, J., & Ott, M. (2014). Gamification and education: A literature review. In C. Busch (Ed.), *Proceedings of the 8th European Conference on Games Based Learning (ECGBL 2014)* (Vol. 1, pp. 50–57). Academic Conferences Ltd.
- Codish, D., & Ravid, D. (2015). Detecting playfulness in educational gamification through behavior patterns. *IBM Journal of Research & Development*, 59(6), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1147/JRD.2015.2459651>
- Cruaud, C. (2018). The playful frame: Gamification in a French-as-a-foreign-language class. *Innovation in Language Learning and Teaching*, 12(4), 330-343. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17501229.2016.1213268>
- Chou, Y. (2019). *Actionable gamification: Beyond points, badges, and leaderboards*. Packt Publishing Ltd.
- Dicheva, D., Dichev, C., Agre, G., & Angelova, G. (2015). Gamification in education: A systematic mapping study. *Educational Technology & Society*, 18(3), 75–88.
- Hamari, J., Shernoff, D. J., Rowe, E., Coller, B., Asbell-Clarke, J., & Edwards, T. (2016). Challenging games help students learn: An empirical study on engagement, flow and immersion in game-based learning. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 54, 170–179. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2015.07.045>
- Huang, W. H., & Soman, D. (2013). *A practitioner's guide to gamification of education*. Rotman School of Management, University of Toronto.
- Jones, S. (2014). *Gamification: Practical strategies for your courses* [PowerPoint slides]. Slideshare. <https://www.slideshare.net/autnes/gamification-practical-strategies-for-your-courses-nov-21-2014>
- K12 Insight. (2012). *Las Cruces student engagement survey*. Las Cruces Public Schools. <http://lcps.k12.nm.us/>
- Kelle, S., Klemke, R., & Specht, M. (2013). Effects of game design patterns on basic life support training content. *Educational Technology & Society*, 16(1), 275-285.
- Lajord, R. K. (2016). *The Gamified Classroom: "It has been different because we know what we are talking about"* [Master's thesis]. The Arctic University of Norway. <https://munin.uit.no/bitstream/handle/10037/9564/thesis.pdf?sequence=2&isAllowed=y>
- McDaniel, R., & Fanfarelli, J. (2016). Building better digital badges: Pairing completion logic with psychological factors. *Simulation & Gaming*, 47(1), 73–102. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046878115627138>
- Nadolny, L., & Halabi, A. (2016). Student participation and achievement in a large lecture course with game-based learning. *Simulation & Gaming*, 47(1), 51-72. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1046878115620388>
- Poole, S. M., Kemp, E., Williams, K. H., & Patterson, L. (2014). Get your head in the game: Using gamification in business education to connect with Generation Y. *Journal for Excellence in Business Education*, 3(2), 1-9.
- Sablić, M., Rački, Z., and Lesandarić, M. (2015). Teachers' and students' evaluation of selected didactic materials according to the Maria Montessori pedagogy. *Croatian Journal of Education*, 17(3), 755-782.